

Well-Being of the Japanese People

Uriel Halbreich MD*

Correspondence: Uriel Halbreich

Uriel Halbreich, Director, Bio-Behavioral Research, Professor of Psychiatry, SUNY-AB, Buffalo, NY, USA.

Received: 15 May 2026; Accepted: 25 May 2026; Published: 10 Jun 2026

Citation: Uriel Halbreich. Well-Being of the Japanese People. Opinion Article. JJMCCRI. 2026; 1(2): 1-2.

Introduction:

“The accelerated Urbanization in Japan is being driven by the opportunities, especially in high technology as well as other trade, manufacturing and commerce industries.” It impacts Physical and Mental Health and numerous social problems (Halbreich 2021a).

It is accompanied by de-population of rural areas. Migration of ambitious capable young people from the farms and villages to the large metropolitans left the elderly people behind, resulting in accelerated rural population of elderly people and labor shortage. “Almost one third of the Japanese population (29.3%) are older than 65 years which is one of the highest in the world and it is one of the fastest aging nations (WHO,2025).” “The trend of aging is amplified by a low fertility rate which is only 1.2 children per a woman, which results in a decreased population.” Socially the problem is confounded by a high rate of adolescent (15-19Y) fertility.(Gallup,2025).

The rapid changes in parameters of demographics which may be associated with stress (Halbreich,2021c) and cultural changes, especially by the younger people, are challenging. The old-time and probably current emphasis on collective harmony and conformism may give way to the younger generation’s Westernized values and attitudes. The diversity of age-related, professional and housing situations, attitudes and life-styles, highlights the necessity for flexibility, innovation, person-centered and culture sensitivity in assessment and solutions for enhancement of Well-Being of every Japanese person.

Obviously, the operational, efficient and efficacious ap-

plication of Well-Being services must be tailored-to-measure to the local culture, environment and regulations.

It is promising that the World Health Organization (WHO) defined Health (WHO,1946) as “a state of complete Physical, Mental and social Well-Being” and Mental Health is “A state of Well-Being in which every individual realizes his or her potential and can make a contribution to his or her community”.

Comprehensive Well-being should fulfil multiple-requirements:

The basics:

- Food--sustainable nutrition
- Shelter-affordable and adequate housing
- Adequate Income
- Safety
- Physical and Mental Health

As well as:

- Positive purpose
- Hope
- Pursuit of Happiness (Halbreich,2018)
- Vibrant social relationships and connections
- Culturally-relevant Spirituality
- Self confidence
- Appreciation by others
- Efficient Transportation
- Work-Life balance

Therefore, a comprehensive Well-Being should be achieved by a multidisciplinary collaboration of Healthcare professionals, Economists, Social Workers, City and transportation experts, Clergy, community Leaders and government(Halbreichetal,2019).

Operational implementation according to the components of Well-Being requires establishment of adequate and accessible services, especially for vulnerable populations like elderly people, disadvantage populations, adolescent girls and boys. Ideally all services will be provided under one roof, this would encourage clients to benefit from all facets of recommended Well-Being and eliminate the need to be bounced from one location to another. Indeed, collaborations, shared ideas and data and, especially, consultations in almost real-time would enhance individual's benefits and team cohesion. The proposed multidisciplinary Well-Being Center should be embedded in the community and would be a core of the neighborhood community, would be able to develop to serve as an advocate and spoke-agency to its constituency.

Services and activities should be positive and proactive (Shin, Halbreich and Jeste, In press). They should emphasize strength of community and individuals, order and harmony. The center and its professionals will maintain order and prevent disorders and disfunction. The proactive services would include assistance in seeking employment and advice in initial stages. Adaptation of elderly constituency to evolving technologies and directing youth to positive and constructive use of their devices would benefit all. The comprehensive services would prevent stigma of mental and physical disorders as well as poverty and unemployment.

The leadership of a practical multidisciplinary service embedded in the community and suited to its cultural and social values and life-style might be challenging. The leader should be open-minded and flexible, departing from a focus on his/her own specialty and pursue a collaborating team respectful of each other's skills, focusing on the advancement of the Help-seeking person. Indeed he/she should possess management and financial skills, lead by own example, be persuasive and well-spoken

and, most importantly, understand the community needs and be sympathetic to them. He/she should be able to convince the community to embrace the newly established agency, develop feeling of ownership and involvement and lead the Center's team toward integration and adaptation to any change in the environment, technologies or perceptions.

Adaptation should start with the leader.

Conclusion

Japan's changing demographics and rapid urbanization require comprehensive and culturally sensitive approaches to well-being. Community-based multidisciplinary services can help address the diverse needs of the population and enhance the overall quality of life.

References:

1. Gallup. Gallup Reports. 2024–2025.
2. World Health Organization (WHO). World Report. Geneva: WHO; 2026.
3. Halbreich U. Stress-related physical and mental disorders: A new paradigm. *Br J Psychiatry Adv.* 2021; 27: 145–152.
4. Halbreich U. Mental vaccines: Can resilience and adaptation of vulnerable individuals and populations be enhanced before disasters and crises? *Br J Psychiatry Adv.* 2021; 27: 201–203.
5. Halbreich U. Pursuit of happiness, prosperity and health (P-HPH). *Int J Soc Psychiatry.* 2018; 64: 307–308.
6. Halbreich U, Schulze T, Botbol M, et al. Partnerships for interdisciplinary collaborative global well-being. *Asia Pac Psychiatry.* 2019; 11(2): e12366.
7. Halbreich U. Impact of urbanization on mental health. *Int J Psychiatry.* 2021.
8. Shin J, Halbreich U, Jeste D. Positive mental health. *Academia Mental Health and Well-Being.* In press.
9. World Health Organization (WHO). Basic Documents. 45th ed. Geneva: WHO; 2025.

Copyright: © 2026 Uriel Halbreich. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.